

REVOLUTIONIZING INSTRUCTION: A PARADIGM SHIFT IN PRACTICAL TEACHING FOR PRIVATE COLLEGE EDUCATION

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Abstract: In response to the evolving landscape of societal needs and the increasing demand for highly qualified individuals, traditional teaching approaches in application-oriented private undergraduate colleges are falling short of aligning with contemporary expectations. This mismatch between the skills nurtured and market requirements underscores the critical need for innovation and reform in the practical teaching management systems of these institutions. To bridge this gap, this study advocates for a holistic transformation of talent development models, in sync with current social dynamics. Emphasizing the integration of practical teaching within the prevailing socio-political context, we seek to harmonize it with local economic imperatives. Additionally, fostering innovation in teaching philosophies, curricula, and methodologies emerges as a potent means to enhance educational outcomes significantly. By undertaking these strategic initiatives, we aim to instill a robust practical mindset in students, thereby augmenting their comprehensive skill set. This research underscores the pressing requirement for revitalizing the teaching approaches within application-oriented private undergraduate colleges to better equip graduates for the contemporary workforce.

Keywords: Practical teaching management, Talent development, Application-oriented colleges, teaching innovation, Societal needs

Introduction

From the current trend of social development, the demand for talents in society is constantly increasing, but corresponding standards have also been raised. However, the traditional teaching mode of application-oriented private undergraduate colleges cannot align with social demand, leading to a disconnect between the talents cultivated and the market. Therefore, the construction and innovation of the practical teaching management system in application-oriented private undergraduate colleges is urgent. We should optimize the talent training mode based on the current social development situation, and focus on the construction of the current political teaching management system, and fully integrate it with local economic development. In addition, mastering the innovation of teaching concepts, content, and methods can comprehensively improve teaching outcomes, establish good practical awareness for students, and enhance their comprehensive abilities.

1. Overview of Practical Teaching Management System

The practical teaching management system is an important measure to cultivate students' innovative and operational abilities. For private application-oriented undergraduate colleges, it is necessary to build a comprehensive practical teaching management system in order to achieve the expected talent cultivation goals and increase students' employment competitiveness [1]. At present, the practical teaching management system has become the forefront of higher education reform. We should combine our own educational characteristics and explore the practical teaching management system, and pay attention to students' innovation and practical ability

cultivation, and use practical activities as a carrier to improve the efficiency and quality of talent cultivation. In addition, the construction of practical teaching management system should strengthen the connection with the market, integrating local economic development, and innovate teaching content and methods, and continuously transport talents for society.

2. The Significance of Constructing a Practical Teaching Management System in Application Oriented Private Undergraduate Colleges

3.1 Comprehensively Improving the Quality of Practical Teaching

The construction of practical teaching management system is the key to improving the teaching quality of application-oriented private undergraduate colleges, which is conducive to improving the consistency between practical teaching quality and teaching objectives. And make sure that students develop towards the expected direction of talent cultivation. In the practical teaching management system, scientific and standardized teaching management methods can be used to enhance students' professional skills, enabling them to obtain comprehensive training in the practical process, and become excellent talents with solid theoretical and practical abilities in junior high school. In addition, the construction of a practical teaching management system is conducive to overcoming the shortcomings of traditional practical teaching, fully adapting to the development needs of the industry. We need to plan according to the characteristics of different professional disciplines, while changing the teaching team and management system, effectively improving the quality of practical teaching.

3.2 Strengthen the Cultivation of Applied Talents

In recent years, applied talents have become educational goals, and the construction of a practical teaching management system is conducive to achieving this goal in application-oriented private undergraduate colleges. This goal aims to cultivate excellent talents with solid professional knowledge, skills, and familiarity with various production activities, creating favorable conditions for social and economic development. Currently, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges have fully integrated regional economic development and market demand into the construction of practical teaching system, and deepened the professional practical teaching system to supplement traditional teaching content. This not only improves teaching efficiency, but also greatly enhances students' theoretical and practical application levels. In addition, students' innovative awareness and ability have been improved in the process of practical teaching, and their personal comprehensive abilities fully meet the market demand for employment. The practical teaching management system is also more in line with the requirements of cultivating applied talents.

3.3 Enhancing Students' Employment Competitiveness

From the perspective of the construction of practical teaching management system in application oriented private undergraduate colleges, the employment competitiveness of students will be greatly enhanced. Due to a more balanced theoretical and practical teaching in colleges, as well as an improvement in the scientific nature of professional teaching, students can fully master specialized theoretical and practical skills, naturally creating favorable conditions for future employment. In addition, the practical teaching management system of colleges should be based on local economic and market development, and the talents cultivated would naturally fully meet market demand. This is also a fundamental condition for promoting students' employment. Students are proficient in frontline basic knowledge and skills, thus gaining the favor of employers.

4. The Shortcomings of the Practical Teaching Management System in Application-Oriented Private Undergraduate Colleges

At present, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges are unable to smoothly carry out practical teaching due to the influence of educational resources and conditions, and even lack a comprehensive practical teaching management system. Some application-oriented private undergraduate colleges only transfer theoretical teaching to extracurricular venues, without fully exerting the role of practical teaching that is, promoting the application of theoretical knowledge. Therefore, students' practical abilities are always difficult to improve, thereby constraining their development. In addition, there are deficiencies in teaching practice management, such as the lack of

professional education and practical resources, and the inability to establish a comprehensive management system. The responsibilities of teachers in practical teaching are not clear, and sometimes their functions overlap, which may lead to resource waste. From this, it can be seen that there are still shortcomings in the practical teaching management system of private applied undergraduate universities. Effective measures need to be taken to obtain educational resources, improve the practical teaching management system, and promote the stable improvement of students' practical abilities. At the same time, universities lack corresponding assessment and evaluation mechanisms, and have not enriched assessment and evaluation methods and content based on teaching reform, making it difficult to accurately evaluate teaching achievements and students' personal growth.

5. Principles for Constructing a Practical Teaching Management System in Application-Oriented Private Undergraduate Colleges

Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should follow the principles of curriculum practice, professional practice, and social practice in the construction of practical teaching management system, and highlight the characteristics of practical teaching to ensure the applicability of teaching content. Establish a connection between practical teaching and social development to enhance students' professional application and social adaptability. In addition, we also need to establish clear practical teaching goals and directions based on the principles of scientific and standardized practical teaching, combined with market demand, gradually refine teaching content, and fully leverage the role and value of practical teaching. Due to the fact that practical teaching is related to students' employment competitiveness, when constructing a practical teaching management system, it is necessary to optimize teaching content with the goal of talent cultivation, ensure a balance between theoretical and practical teaching, and effectively improve the efficiency and quality of practical teaching.

6. Strategies for Building a Practical Teaching Management System in Application-Oriented Private Undergraduate Colleges

6.1 Update Teaching Concepts and Innovate Teaching Content

Currently, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should update their teaching concepts. We need to innovate in all aspects of teaching content based on modern practical teaching requirements, effectively serve local economic development with professional practice, and clarify specific practical teaching directions. Therefore, universities should clarify the various requirements of the market for professional talents, adapt to market demand and enterprise characteristics in the construction process of practical teaching management system, and continue to pay attention to local economic development trends. For example, in recent years[2], the cultivation of inter-disciplinary talent has become a development trend. Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges must enhance the integration of professional theory and practical teaching, innovate practical teaching content, and serve as a breakthrough point to meet the goals of modern talent cultivation. Due to the fact that practical teaching is related to students' application abilities and is conducive to promoting their comprehensive development, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should clarify the local economic and market development, increase more professional practical teaching content, and use scientific and standardized practical teaching management methods to improve the results of professional practical teaching. In summary, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should conduct market research, and clarify professional practical teaching requirements, educational requirements, and the current situation of regional economic development as a reference for the construction of professional practical teaching management system, effectively improving the practical teaching system, providing comprehensive and scientific practical guidance for students, and meeting their employment development needs.

6.2 Clarify Teaching Objectives and Improve the Teaching System

The practical teaching management objective system of private applied undergraduate universities is divided into multiple aspects, mainly focusing on teaching and management of students' practical abilities. Practical ability of general education. The teaching content is general education courses, and various practical activities are designed based on the organization of natural sciences and humanities and social sciences. Pay

attention to the comprehensive training and evaluation of students, and use the practice of Liberal education to enhance students' social adaptability. In the teaching process, social practice and project training will be highlighted, ultimately achieving the goal of cultivating applied talents.

Basic application ability in the discipline. Simply put, it means that students are able to apply the theories they have mastered to practice, which is also one of the necessary abilities. During the teaching process, students will be led to delve into basic professional norms, clarify specific practical processes, and use various practical activities to exercise their hands-on and analytical abilities. Therefore, most of them are carried out through practical training to gradually cultivate students.

Professional skills and practical abilities. This is also an important link in the integration of theory and practice, with a focus on cultivating students' problem-solving abilities and being exposed to job positions through internships and practical training. Cultivate students' familiarity and understanding of professional positions in their senior stage[3].

Comprehensive practical application ability. Students need to have a certain level of interdisciplinary knowledge integration and application ability, independent thinking and team cooperation ability. Presented through school enterprise cooperation and integration of industry and education, independent design and production, vocational skills competitions, and other activities will be arranged for students to cultivate their practical awareness and abilities.

6.3 Improve the Management System and Provide Teaching Guarantee

In the construction of practical teaching management system, management is also an indispensable part. Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should create a management system that conforms to educational characteristics based on their own development status, and gradually refine the practical teaching management system based on teaching preparation, organizational implementation, quality supervision, and assessment evaluation, in order to provide guarantees for the development of practical teaching. The practical teaching management system is divided into multiple parts.

The practical teaching management system. A scientific institutional system can play an effective restraining role and should be designed based on the teaching reality, objectives, content, and requirements.

Practical teaching management organization. Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges can establish practical teaching management institutions or departments, such as practical training management centers, with a focus on practical teaching management, clarifying departmental responsibilities and job functions, and strengthening the supervision and management of practical teaching activities both on and off campus [4]. At the same time, a practical teaching expert committee should be established, mainly composed of enterprise technical personnel and teachers, responsible for practical teaching consultation and providing suggestions for optimizing practical teaching.

Practical teaching process management. For practical teaching, strict control over various processes and links is also an important condition for improving the efficiency and quality of practical teaching. In the preparation stage of teaching, the focus should be on researching institutional policies, how to set up practical teaching content, and how to develop teaching plans, so that teachers can improve the practical teaching system from multiple dimensions.

6.4 Implement the Assessment System and Conduct Effective Evaluation

Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should have a comprehensive practical teaching assessment system. Evaluate teaching outcomes and students to ensure the effectiveness of practical teaching management. Firstly, specific evaluation criteria, implementation, content, and methods of practical teaching should be clearly defined. Targeted evaluation should be conducted on students, while paying attention to the evaluation of practical teaching processes. We should not only focus on the results, otherwise we will lose fairness and objectivity. Moreover, evaluating from multiple dimensions is easier to analyze the effectiveness of practical teaching. Secondly, it is necessary to optimize the management of practical teaching assessment. Schools can create

diversified practical teaching assessment and evaluation methods, fully utilize innovative achievement assessment, and incorporate all aspects of invention and production in practical teaching into the assessment scope to enhance the comprehensiveness of assessment and evaluation. In addition, refining the assessment and evaluation content can provide more detailed evaluations for practical teaching, and the evaluation results can serve as a reference for teaching optimization. The evaluation subject is divided into teacher evaluation and student evaluation. Teachers should strive to participate in the construction of the practical teaching system, and implement the practical teaching tasks by doing the most basic evaluation work well. Students can also participate in the evaluation process, such as in group evaluations, recognizing other students' practical innovation abilities, learning from each other, and effectively improving practical teaching outcomes.

6.5 Deepen School Enterprise Cooperation and Build a Practical Platform

The cooperation between schools and enterprises is undoubtedly the fundamental condition for promoting the construction of practical teaching systems in private applied undergraduate universities. The main focus is on resource interaction between universities and enterprises, with the employment needs of enterprises as the goal of talent cultivation. In the process of practical teaching, coordination, interaction and sharing are well done to create a long-term cooperation model. On the one hand, it is beneficial to enrich practical teaching resources, and on the other hand, the talents cultivated can seamlessly connect with the market. Therefore, school enterprise cooperation has become an important direction for university reform. Application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should strengthen cooperation with local enterprises, fully utilize enterprise resources to create practical teaching platforms, provide students with specialized practice venues, and fundamentally improve the quality of practical teaching. Many private applied undergraduate universities are affected by insufficient educational resources and hardware conditions, making it impossible to build a more scientific and comprehensive practical teaching system. However, cooperation between schools and enterprises has become an opportunity, and enterprises can provide relevant technology and resources for application-oriented private undergraduate colleges to ensure the smooth implementation of practical teaching[5]. In order to break the previous practice teaching restrictions, we can make innovations such as creating a practice teaching place based on the industrial value chain, highlighting the authenticity of practice teaching, building a virtual simulation laboratory platform, deeply developing students' practical potential, or creating a virtual experiment teaching platform based on modern technology, applying various modern technologies, including big data, cloud computing, etc., to build an open and interactive network practice teaching. Through the above measures, we will comprehensively promote the reform of practical teaching in private applied undergraduate universities.

6.6 Building a Teaching Staff Based on the Integration of Industry and Education

The integration of industry and education is a modern education concept, which mainly refers to the full combination of teaching and industry, and the ability to build a practical teaching system based on the needs of the industry, so as to cultivate more outstanding talents. At present, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should promote the integration of industry and education, build a practical teaching management system and teaching staff based on this concept, strengthen the correlation between practical teaching and industry development, and attract more enterprises to participate in the talent cultivation process, truly achieving seamless integration between talent cultivation and the market. For example, in the process of practical teaching, to create a more realistic job environment for students, many universities will conduct practical teaching simulations based on enterprise production, provide professional training operations, let students understand the job environment, continuously hone their practical skills, and effectively improve the results of practical teaching. In addition, based on the concept of integrating industry and education, we need to create a professional teaching team, such as a "Double Qualified Teacher Team", which has strong theoretical foundation and practical abilities. At the same time, we have rich teaching experience and participated in various scientific research projects. By ensuring the ability level of teachers, we can effectively cultivate students' practical abilities.

7. Conclusions

For application-oriented private undergraduate colleges, the construction of a practical teaching management system is a necessary path to promote professional teaching reform and innovation. It is conducive to improving students' practical ability cultivation, deepening professional theoretical Knowledge, enhancing students' employability, and also helping them adapt to job positions in advance. In addition, in the context of modern society, practical and applied talents have become the training goal. Therefore, application-oriented private undergraduate colleges should strengthen the construction of practical teaching management systems, break the traditional limitations of single theoretical teaching, enrich practical teaching methods and content, and promote talent cultivation to meet market demand. Therefore, universities should clarify the value of practical education and strengthen cooperation between schools and enterprises, based on the concept of integration of industry and education, improve the effectiveness of practical education, organize students to carry out diversified practical activities, and lay a good foundation for their own development and future employment.

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